

DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF BASIC ELECTRONICS TRAINER

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ABSTRACT

Design and construction of various trainers, prototypes and/ or simulators in most schools in teaching the fundamental concepts of electronics and electricity has been long proven to be effective in schools as it provides real- life situations and conditions to imitate circuits and other related technical conditions. This study was aimed to design and evaluate a Basic Electronics Trainer, to help improve teaching the basics of the course Electronics to would-be technicians. The use of this apparatus will be maximized since the apparatus can provide students with series of laboratory activities that would enhance their understanding of the work, functions, circuit connections, and applications of basic electronic devices which are all essential in understanding the building blocks of electronic products. This study presents the basic concept of designing and constructing the trainer. Simulations and experiments are based on the fundamental operations of power supply circuits and other experiments and activities focused on the theory of operation of semiconductor devices such as diodes, transistors, thyristors and integrated circuit regulators. Using locally-available components, devices and instruments, the trainer presented herein proved to be feasible as an alternative resource against costly commercially-made trainers in the market that offer similar training/ learning outputs. Based on the evaluation conducted by select-experts and field technicians in the locality as to the workability, effectiveness, durability, aesthetics and safety, the trainer was found out to be highly acceptable. Furthermore, this study comes with an Activity Manual to provide at least a substantial number of experiments on basic theoretical concept of operation in Electronics technology, thus proving the usability of the trainer.

Keywords: *electronics and electrical technology, trainers design, prototype*

INTRODUCTION

Today, our society has come to a point where almost every person in all walks of life is greatly influenced by technological breakthroughs brought about by electronics. Every day, thousands of people around the world buy their needed appliances such as television and radio receivers, home theatre systems, video players and recorders, microwave ovens, air conditioning units, telephones, personal computer units, and many others. In our country alone, our government has spent billions of pesos in purchasing electronic goods used in transportation, communication, medical diagnosis and treatment, agriculture, crime detection, traffic control and many more for the last five years. With the growing demand for electronic products used for household and industry, the increase in the need for skilled manpower which would serve as assemblers, installers, repair and maintenance workers, and electronic products specialists have also grown inevitably.

Because of the clear demand by the electronics industry for skilled electronic technicians and product specialists, the Philippine school system, specifically those offering technology courses are challenged to train and produce the needed manpower by the industry. In line with this challenge, the schools in the country are expected to produce quality technical and vocational training that will conform to the standards set by the electronics industry. Knowing the promising career that awaits every electronics technology student, in the electronics industry, basic and advanced courses in Electronics have become one of the main program offerings in many technical and vocational schools all over the country. Recent enrolment records in the country now show the dramatic increase in the number of students in the course.

For the schools to be able to produce competent graduates equipped with standard skills needed for employment, these technical and vocational schools must at least provide the students with relevant laboratory facilities, rich learning activities and technical training. In order to attain a more effective and meaningful teaching and learning activities in electronics course, shop teachers and students must be exposed to relevant learning materials, resources, demonstration and practical laboratory activities. Shop fundamentals and laboratory principles that are properly taught by technology instructors are more effectively learned by students and become more permanent in their hearts and minds when they are given the opportunity to experience actual “hands-on” activities on various laboratory experiments. In addition, basic theories and principles of electronic devices and apparatuses are best understood when actual activities on their practical uses and applications are given emphasis.

But the problem lies mostly with most technical schools having little or no appropriate tools, equipment, laboratory apparatuses, experiment manuals and trainers in electronics laboratory classes. As a result of this, the quality of education that their graduates possess, in terms of knowledge and skills, do not match the standard competencies needed by the industry because of inadequate training facilities. In Isabela State University-Ilagan Campus alone, one of the perennial problems confronted by the school is the inadequacy, or worse,

the absence of appropriate and relevant laboratory equipment in most shop classes due to cost-cutting of budget intended for laboratory equipment, gadgets and apparatuses. The situation becomes more difficult when students continue to flock to technology courses despite the lack of these training facilities in the class.

In the course Electronics Technology for instance, the enrolment this school year has peaked to its maximum and to the instructors' and students' dismay, still not even a single training gadget or apparatus was procured to at least partially ease the need for a training apparatus. The quality of technical training, sought by students, through relevant and appropriate training activities in Electronics Technology has been greatly affected and compromised. As a consequence of this, instructors of Electronics Technology were deprived of their privilege to teach their respective fields of specialization competently and on the other hand, students enrolled in the course were also denied of their right to a better and more relevant technical training through adequate laboratory facility.

With this reality, the electronics instructor is therefore challenged to find ways and means to partially solve the existing problem. Amidst this situation, the initiative and resourcefulness of the instructor is sought to design and improvise training equipment made from supplies and materials found in the local market as a cheaper alternative for commercially-available equipment. With the present problem on the inadequacy of laboratory learning equipment in Electronics Technology course, the researcher, came up with this idea of conducting this study to introduce new learning experiences in the course and to eventually sustain the student's interest to pursue his chosen career.

The researcher strongly believes that with the construction of this proposed Basic Electronics Trainer, teaching the basics of the course to would-be technicians will be greatly improved and the use of this apparatus will be maximized since the apparatus can provide students with series of laboratory activities that would enhance their understanding of the work, functions, circuit connections, and applications of basic electronic devices which are all essential in understanding the building blocks of electronic products.

Research Objectives

This study aimed to develop and evaluate a Basic Electronics Trainer for Electronics Technology students of Isabela State University-Ilagan Campus.

More specifically, it sought to achieve the following objectives:

1. design and construct a Basic Electronics Trainer;
2. test the functionality of the apparatus by conducting various experiments concerning practical electronic circuits through the use and application of active and passive electronic devices;
3. revise the gadget based on the results of the tests on the apparatus to further improve its existing features and capabilities; and
4. determine the level of acceptability of the developed Basic Electronics Trainer in terms of:
 - a. design
 - b. construction
 - c. functionality, and

d. safety

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a mixed-method research design namely, the Project Development Method (PDM) because the researcher conceptualized the design and specifications of the Basic Electronics Trainer, and use the descriptive method of research in his study to obtain reliable, consistent, and actual results. Various authorities define descriptive research as a scientific method which involves observing and describing the behavior of a subject without influencing it in any way. This type of research is used to describe the data and characteristics about what is being studied. Although the data description is factual, accurate and systematic, the research cannot describe what caused a situation. In other words, descriptive research can be said to have a low requirement for internal validity.

The respondents of the study were selected technology instructors from the College of Industrial Technology and Education and from the College of Electrical and Electronics Engineering of the Isabela State University-Ilagan Campus, Ilagan, Isabela. Technology teachers from the nearby technical / vocational school offering Radio Mechanics were also tapped to evaluate the project. A number of technicians from different electronics shops and centers in the locality were also invited by the researcher to evaluate his work.

Table 1. Distribution of the Teacher/Technician Respondents of the Study

Teacher / Technican Respondents by Name of Schools and Shops	Population	Actual Sample Size	Percentage
Isabela State University-Ilagan Campus	8	8	100
Isabela School of Arts and Trades-Ilagan	2	1	50
San Jose Reyes Robotics Center - Ilagan	2	2	50
BOY Electronics Shop-Calamagui	2	1	50
FRANCIS Electronics Service Center-Baligatan	2	1	50
SANTOS Audio/Video Center- Baligatan	1	1	100
OBENA'S Electronics Shop – Cauayan City	1	1	100
Total	18	15	83

Knowing the capability and competence of these instructors, teachers and technicians in the field, the researcher has chosen them to evaluate the Trainer. These respondents were asked to accomplish an evaluation form that determines the acceptability and functionality of the trainer

Figure 1. Composition of Respondents of the Study by Profession

The pie chart shown in **Figure 1** shows the composition of respondents who conducted evaluation of the project. The total respondents were composed of two (2) Electronics Engineers, eight (8) Instructors teaching Electronics and Electricity, one (1) Radio Mechanics Teacher from the secondary school and four (4) shop technicians from different electronics service centers and shops in the locality.

Various ways on how to gather and collect the appropriate data needed in the development of the basic electronics trainer were considered by the researcher. These data, which is in a form of figures obtained from surveys, was used by the researcher to draw conclusions on his project. Data is an essential part in conducting the study and in developing the project.

Before the researcher could conduct the evaluation of his project, formal invitations to target respondents, through their school administrators and superiors were made by the researcher and countersigned by his adviser. Letters were sent to Isabela State University-

Ilagan, Isabela School of Arts and Trades, San Jose Reyes Robotics Center, and to different electronics repair shops and centers in the locality.

The evaluation of the project was conducted at the Industrial Technology Building of ISU-Ilagan. Respondents from nearby technical schools and electronics service centers/shops were invited to personally inspect the gadget, perform activities on the trainer and accomplish evaluation forms or questionnaires. The evaluation questionnaire used in the study was based and adopted some instruments used by Canceran (2019), Corbillon (2019) and Makabenta (2019) in their studies, however, to make them more effective and appropriate, some improvements and modifications were made by the researchers on these instruments. The modified instrument let the respondents evaluate the developed trainer as to its design, construction, functionality, and, safety.

In order to analyze the collected data, the statistical tool used in this study is the weighted mean. This was computed to find out the acceptability of the project as perceived by the respondents. The scale shown in the following pages was used to interpret the computed weighted mean for each indicator.

SCALE	VERBAL DESCRIPTION
4.21—5.0	Highly Acceptable
3.41—4.20	Acceptable
2.61—3.40	Unacceptable
1.81—2.60	Moderately Unacceptable
1.0—1.80	Highly Unacceptable

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To further enrich his understanding of the study, the researchers used library materials such as books, journals, newsletters and other related studies about educational technology projects and the development of trainers used in electrical and electronics instruction. Websites were used extensively to carefully examine of internet articles about construction of trainers that bear direct significance to the study were also conducted to give the researcher additional information and facts needed in developing the project.

1. Design and Construction of the Proposed Project

The programs of works for the construction of the Basic Electronics Trainer are as follows:

- A. Planning.** This involves the drawing of schematic diagrams to provide useful illustrations of circuits of the project.

Figure 2. Standard Pin Assignment of an LM317 Voltage Regulator IC

Figure 3. Schematic Diagram of the Variable DC Power Supply, Multiple Output AC Power Supply, and Digital Logic LED Display.

Figure 4. Schematic Diagram of the +5 Volts DC Regulator Using 7805 IC

B. Designing and Lay-outing. This refers the making of circuit designs and drawing plans for the project.

Figure 5. Snapshot of the Stickers Designed on the Computer and Lay-outing the Stickers on the Acrylic Board

Figure 6. Layout Design of the Trainer Panel Indicating the Actual Locations of Devices and Instruments

Figure 7. Front and Side View of the Basic Electronics Trainer

Figure 8. Perspective Drawing of the Basic Electronics Trainer

C. Constructing the Basic Electronics Trainer.

For the construction of the project, the following were taken into consideration:

The constructed Basic Electronics Trainer was suited to the curriculum/subjects of BS Industrial Technology major in Electronics and Electrical Technology and industry experts' level of understanding. The trainer was constructed utilizing used electrical devices from different firms locally and commercially available materials and supplies.

The first step in constructing the project is to prepare the necessary supplies, materials, tools and equipment. cut the acrylic sheet to the specified dimensions (38"x48") with an acrylic cutter tool, followed by removing the acrylic protective cover. The fourth step is to apply the stickers to the acrylic board according to the layout design of the trainer panel. The fifth step is to drill holes for the banana jacks that will connect components, devices, and the activity board. The sixth step is to cut compartment holes for additional devices like panel meters and test instruments. Finally, install banana jacks in all of the terminal holes.

2. Testing of the developed Project

Figure 9. Photo of the Researcher Conducting the Actual Testing of the Trainer

This is the stage wherein the project is put on its operation where power is applied to the transformers and power supplies. The actual testing of all the experiments on the Activity Manual is performed by the researcher. All observations, corrections and modifications during this process were recorded and filed.

3. Revision of the developed Project

In order to improve the operations of the trainer, a series of try-outs and testing were conducted right after the project has been completed. A number of defects were diagnosed during the testing period. To be able to correct the faults, corrections were made to resolve the defects on the trainer.

Table 2. Defects found and Revisions Made

Defects	Changes Made
1. Erratic voltage readings on the AC panel meter.	Connected a diode to the panel meter convert AC to DC.
2. Waveform displayed is erroneous.	Repaired ground connection of the oscilloscope test probe.
3. + 5 volts DC reading too high.	Improper pin connection of the 7805 IC.
4. Thermistor is not exhibiting normal resistance reading when exposed to heat	Thermistor is positioned as close as possible to the heater resistor.
5. Thermistor 12v-lamp shuts down during operation.	Replaced a smaller 12-v bulb with a much higher filament resistance

Figure 10. Photos of the Completed Basic Electronics Trainer

Description of the Completed Project

The following paragraphs discuss the parts and function, interrelationship of the parts, limitations and capabilities of the project.

- 1. Parts and Functions.** The parts and functions of the Basic Electronics Trainer and its function are listed and discussed below:

2. Panel Board. This is the main activity board made of acrylic plastic material mounted a wooden frame. All components and devices needed in performing various laboratory activities and interconnecting them are mounted at the back. Terminals for these components and devices are accessed only through its corresponding banana jacks. The back panel is covered by a much thinner clear acrylic plastic to let students take a view on how the trainer was constructed. The project is specifically designed as a demonstration gadget to clearly show and prove the basic principles behind electronic components and devices.

3. AC and DC Power Supply Modules. These circuits provide the needed varying amount of AC and DC voltages for the various laboratory activities in the project. The AC power supply has a selector switch to instantly shift voltage output of 3v, 4.5v, 6v, 9v and 12 vAC. Similarly, the DC power supply produces a varying amount of 1.3v to 30 vDC.

4. Connect-All Activity Board. This part of the project provides the interconnection of components and devices. Similar to a breadboard activity board principle, an array of vertical and horizontal banana jacks are interconnected to form the activity board. Assembling of the different circuits is done through banana plugs or connectors. All banana plugs and jacks were of heavy-duty material and the wire used for the connectors is automotive wire No. 16 to ensure durability.

5. Table, Drawer and Cabinet. The table is made up of a $\frac{3}{4}$ -inch thick plywood that functions as the base for the project. A drawer and a cabinet are provided for storing connectors, tools, materials and test equipment.

6. Component Modules and Assembly. The components used in the project are all found on the panel board and individually labeled. Schematic symbols and diagrams are also shown to help the user of the project identify the correct polarity and pin configurations of components and devices.

7. Test Equipment. Digital and analog multimeters are mounted on the trainer to be used in voltage and resistance reading, component testing and comparing voltage readings. A compartment for an oscilloscope is also provided on the lower right portion of the panel. The oscilloscope will be used in demonstrating the voltage waveform of various signals.

8. Main AC Panel Control. This is located at the back portion of the trainer wherein instruments for controlling and monitoring the 220-VAC line are performed. As a safety feature, the project is equipped with a circuit breaker and a main switch to switch on and shut down the main AC power line.

Features of the Project

The completed project can be used for visual instruction and as activity and experiment board for individual or group use. The project is also found to be convenient and safe to use. As a visual instruction device, the project can be used to demonstrate operating principles of basic components such as resistors, capacitors, diodes, transistors,

transformers, and integrated circuit. Various circuit can be assembled to prove the capabilities of active and passive components to make significant changes to the characteristics and amount of voltage. Since test instruments such as multi-meters and oscilloscope are provided, the trainer can be used for demonstrating various experiments that needed monitoring of the amount and waveforms of voltages.

As an activity board, the project can be used by individual or group of students in performing the different laboratory activities prescribed in the Activity manual. Since the project uses banana connectors to interconnect the different components and devices, soldering and de-soldering of parts in assembling the circuits are eliminated, thus making the project convenient and efficient to use. Fuses and circuit breakers are also installed on the primary and secondary circuits of the power supply system, ensuring that the power is cut off during short circuits. Users of the trainer are ensured that they are insulated from the 220-vAC line because the trainer back panel is covered with a clear acrylic plastic sheet. The user of the trainer will only be working on low DC voltages ranging from 1.3vDC to 30vDC, rated at 1.5 amperes, thus making the user safe from electrical shocks. A cooling fan is also installed to make sure that power transformers and other heat-generating devices are cooled during operation.

The main panel board and table of project are designed to be detached from each other to facilitate the transportation of the device from one place to another. At least ten (10) metal screws hold the main trainer panel to the base/table. Ball casters are also installed to easily move the project around a certain place. Ball casters can be locked to put the apparatus intact during actual use.

4. Evaluation of the Project

One of the important elements of the study is the evaluation of the completed Basic Electronics Trainer and its Activity Manual.

The table on the following page shows the summary of the evaluation and the mean rating for each criterion on the acceptability of the trainer along with the corresponding verbal interpretation.

Table 3. Summary of the Ratings Given by Respondents on the Acceptability of the Completed Project

CRITERIA AND INDICATORS	RATING	
	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
A. Design		
1. The frame and base of the trainer is stable.	5.0	Highly Acceptable
2. The dimensions of the parts are proportion.	5.0	Highly Acceptable
3. The devices and components are in order and		Highly Acceptable

accessible.	4.86	
4. Labels and symbols on the panel are visible.	4.66	Highly Acceptable
5. Storage for tools, materials and equipment are provided in the trainer.	5.0	Highly Acceptable
AVERAGE	4.90	Highly Acceptable
B. Construction		
1. The setup of the internal parts is organized.	4.86	Highly Acceptable
2. The materials used in the construction of the trainer are durable.	4.86	Highly Acceptable
3. The connections of devices, parts and components are neatly done.	4.6	Highly Acceptable
4. All the devices and components are purposeful/ useful.	4.73	Highly Acceptable
5. The general construction of the trainer is well done.	4.86	Highly Acceptable
6. The cost of the trainer is reasonable.	4.93	Highly Acceptable
7. The parts of the trainer are locally available.	4.93	Highly Acceptable
AVERAGE	4.82	Highly Acceptable
C. Functionality		
1. The trainer panel is easy to use and operate.	4.66	Highly Acceptable
2. The trainer has a low maintenance needs.	4.93	Highly Acceptable
3. The trainer serves the purpose of a basic electronics trainer.	4.8	Highly Acceptable
4. Activities and experiments can be performed on the activity board.	5.0	Highly Acceptable
5. The trainer can be used by students individually or by group.	5.0	Highly Acceptable
AVERAGE	4.87	Highly Acceptable
D. Safety		
1. The design of the trainer enables the user to work safely.	5.0	Highly Acceptable
2. The 220-volt line is insulated making the trainer safe to use.	4.93	Highly Acceptable
3. The trainer provides activities and experiments that use low voltage.	5.0	Highly Acceptable
4. Safety devices such as fuse and breakers are installed		Highly Acceptable

on the trainer.	4.8	
AVERAGE	4.93	Highly Acceptable
Overall Mean	4.88	Highly Acceptable

Based from the results obtained, the completed Basic Electronics Trainer received mean ratings of 4.90, 4.82, 4.87 and 4.93 for the design, construction, functionality and safety, respectively. The instructional gadget was perceived to be highly acceptable by the respondents in all the criteria presented. The computed overall mean is 4.88 which suggest that the trainer is highly acceptable. It can also be said that the constructed trainer is well designed and durable, functional, safe to use, easy to maintain and of lower cost.

The results agreed by the findings of Milkić et al. (2018) found that using a trainer in a laboratory setting can help students learn new skills and knowledge. Furthermore, it was demonstrated that the developed trainer can serve as a solid foundation for the creation of new teaching methods for academic studies in renewable energy

In the same vein, Santos (2019) study found that his constructed trainer was suitable for addressing the inadequacy of training equipment used both in electrical and electronics technology.

Conclusions

The basic electronics trainer can be constructed using locally available materials and resources. The trainer is feasible and highly acceptable for instructional purposes. The trainer has been meticulously designed and built to meet the needs of educational curricula as well as industry standards. Electronics Engineers, Instructors teaching Electronics and Electricity, Radio Mechanics Teachers from secondary schools, and shop technicians from various electronics service centers and shops. All of them gave the trainer high ratings for design, construction, functionality, and safety. This emphasizes the significance of considering diverse perspectives when designing educational tools.

Recommendations

Based on the above-mentioned findings and conclusions, the following recommendations were cited:

1. school administrators should encourage other technology instructors to develop other related instructional apparatus to further improve teaching-learning in electronics;
2. technology instructors in other technology areas should be encouraged to conduct similar study to improve instruction in their respective fields;
3. budget and financial assistance should be extended to researchers who are conducting similar studies;
4. other trainers should be developed to provide a wider coverage in the teaching of basic electronics; and

5. similar and much improved trainers should be fabricated to be used by other departments in the campus.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Following ethical standards, this research adheres to principles of integrity, respect, and responsibility towards all the participants involved. Before the conduct of the basic electronics trainer, the researcher obtained informed consent from the participants, ensuring their understanding of the study's purpose, procedures, and potential risks. Confidentiality and anonymity were preserved throughout data collection, analysis, and dissemination, safeguarding participants' privacy. Moreover, the researcher made sure that there was no conflict of interest in conducting the study, avoided plagiarism issues, and no bias was made in the interpretation of the results of the study. Finally, he ensured that the findings were used only for the research.

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